
The Role of Digital Technologies in the Field of Museum Study

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Annotation. *This article provides scientific analyzes of the modernization of the field of museology through digital technologies, as well as its role.*

Keywords: *virtual museum, URI address system, HTML, web exhibition, 3D, DiMoDa online.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, museums are a social institution, and modern technologies are used to display museum objects in the implementation of several tasks, such as how museums are today, how to attract visitors. In the age of 21st century technologies, museums being active on the Internet and having their own websites will effectively increase the number and interest of visitors. After all, the Internet, which is a modern postal service, is a means of communication in every field, saves time and increases the efficiency of work. Information on the Internet grows rapidly and reaches almost all parts of the world. The most powerful advertising in attracting people's attention is done through the Internet. It can easily implement various opportunities such as various purchases, admission to higher education institutions, participation in online conferences, dating, various ways of earning money, job search, information, books on various topics. A number of decisions and laws have been adopted to further develop and improve museums in accordance with the requirements of the times, in order to form young people's feelings of love, loyalty and pride for the Motherland. Scientific sources include J.Kh. Ismailova "Fundamentals of modern museology"¹, J.Kh. Ismailova, K.S.Nishanova and M.S. Muhamedova's "Museum and Society"², M.

¹ Исмаилова Ж.Х. Замонавий музейшунослик асослари. – Т: Турон Замин Зиё. 2016 . – Б.208

² Исмаилова Ж.Х., Нишонова К.С., Мухамедова М.С. Iarning Музей ва жамият. – Т: Чинор ЭНК. 2015. – Б.176.

Arends. D. Goldfarb. D. Merkle, "Interaction with art museums on the web"³ by M. Weingartner, P.F. From the works of Marty "Museum websites and museum visitors: Digital museum resources and their use"⁴, L. Ya. Nolin's "Internet site and data museum", M.V. A lot of information can be found in Legechenko's articles entitled "Nekotorye aspekty kultury sozdaniya muzejnogo web-sayta".

The activity of museums on the Internet creates many conveniences for viewers of different ages and representatives of this field. For these reasons, it is important to study the museum sites in order to cover the activities of the museum on the Internet. Therefore, the Ministry of Culture, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development, the State Committee for Tourism Development, the Academy of Arts, interested ministries and agencies jointly developed the following projects for the implementation of the "Virtual Museum" project:

- creation of 3D and audio formats of 2 thousand rarest museum objects in 6 languages;
- to ensure that touristic museum sites are maintained in 6 world languages;
- Placing the "Virtual Museum" database on the Internet sites of the National Library of Uzbekistan, regional information-library centers, and large tourist companies.⁵

If we look at history, discoveries are very important in the world of science. The communication network called the spider's web was one such discovery. The first website was created in 1990 by a scientist named Tim Berners Lee. It is based on HTTP data, URI address system and HTML systems in Latin www, which means World Wide Web technology. The first site named info.cern.ch contains the principles of server and browser operation and creation, so as a result, this site became the world's first internet directory. Later, Tim Berners-Lee posted other site applications on this site. This site was formed over the years based on the idea of quick information transfer during World War II. The site can be viewed at <http://info.cern.ch/hypertext/WWW/TheProject.html>.⁶

³ M. Arends. D. Goldfarb. D. Merkl M. Weingartner. Interaction with art museums on the web. – Vienna: Institute of Software Technology and Interactive Systems, Vienna University of Technology Favoritenstrasse. 2009

⁴ Marty P.F. Museum websites and museum visitors: Digital museum resources and their use. – Florida: College of Information. Florida State University. 2007

⁵ <http://uz.infocom.uz/2014/02/17/virtual-muzey-yaratish-texnologiyasi-va-amaliyotda-qollash-tajribasidan/>

⁶ <https://masterok.livejournal.com/2056729.html>

Since the 90s of the 20th century, various large companies began to create their own sites on the Internet. Famous companies such as large pizza companies, McDonalds, large car manufacturers, newspapers and magazines have started to create their own pages. In 1992, for the first time, the Virtual Museum was developed by the Apple Computer Company as a test. It was distributed free of charge in the form of CD-ROM to thousands of major schools, universities and museums around the world. This Virtual Museum was created in 3D format, and the person using it could easily transfer the 3D format object from one place to another and play as a game or organize an exposition by himself. The project was created by a team of graphic designers led by Frank Crowe, Miller, Eric Hoffert, Shenchang Eriv Chen, Elizabeth Patterson, Dean Blackketter, Steve Rubin, Sally Epplin, Derrick Yim and Jim Hanan. The next created Virtual Museum belongs to the Guggenheim Museum in 1999.

"Virtual" means "almost", "close", so VM is a museum close to reality. The first online museums were few. Pages were much simpler, slower, multimedia technology possibilities were much less than today. In 1993, the Museum of Computer Art (MOCA-Museum of Computer Art) was established under the New York State Department of Education, and in 2002, it was named a top museum by the Museum Management Association. MOCA Virtual Museum <http://moca.virtual.museum> has several exhibitions from 2000 to 2019. According to the format of these exhibitions, it is possible to buy online at prices from 55 US dollars to 119 US dollars.

In 1994, the website of the artist Lin Hsin Hsin's art museum of the same name was created in Singapore. This site has an unusual design. The fact that the background is blue and the writing is white makes it a bit difficult to read the words. But the unusual thing is that its sections are written in a poetic manner. The History of Science Museum in Oxford was founded in 1683, and its website was created on August 21, 1995. Compared to other museums, this museum was able to create its web page much earlier due to its high capabilities.

Ljubljana Open Air Museum was established in 1993. The website has been operating since 1996. The exhibition halls of this huge museum located in the capital of Slovenia include expositions of urban architecture and building interiors. Their idea was to show an interactive map and a virtual panorama. The goal of this project was to organize a virtual visit to the museum as "3D" and to restore the completed exhibition to a real state.

Founded in 1994, New York's Virtual Museum of Computing website lists all websites related to the history of computers and computer science.

The Israel Museum in Jerusalem had a website in 1996. The Asia Society Virtual Gallery was established in 1998, dedicated to the exhibition "Looks beyond contact".

The Los Angeles Museum of Natural History was founded in 1910, and the museum and website were launched in 1998. The museum is the largest natural and history museum in the western United States and an active research center.

WebExhibition was created in 1999 and is an interactive concept-based web museum that encourages the visitor to think deeply about scientific discoveries and cultural processes in a new way. Among such exhibitions, virtual exhibitions such as "Pigments over the centuries", "Butter", "Van Gogh's letters", "Sharia over the centuries", "Calendar over the centuries" were held.

The site of the Science Museum in London was also created in 1999. The creation of the first website in the United Kingdom was achieved with the help of King's College.

The site of the Tilakin Museum was launched in 1999. This museum is an online science and educational resource with the primary goal of understanding, raising awareness about the biology and, hopefully, the history of the Tasmanian tiger.

Websites are the face of the museum, that is, they represent it. This places great responsibility on the person who creates it and displays it. According to the rules of multimedia technology, websites should mainly have the following sections:⁷

- Information about the activities of the museum;
- Museum history;
- Information about the museum collection;
- Information about museum exposition;
- Information about exhibitions;
- Report on scientific activity;
- To have an educational systematic goal;

⁷ M. Arends. D. Goldfarb. D. Merkl M. Weingartner. "Interaction with art museums on the web". – Vienna: Institute of Software Technology and Interactive Systems, Vienna University of Technology Favoritenstrasse. 2009. P-8

- Search system;
- Guest book;
- There should be information about the license of the site.

By the 2000s, some shortcomings began to appear on the museum sites. In particular, there were problems with downloading photos posted on the site. Similar situations happened in the Berlin History Museum and the San Francisco Museum of Fine Arts. But together with the developer companies, these problems have been solved.

In 1998, the site of Russian museums was established on the basis of the "International Museum Server" project. It includes a list of 200 official and unofficial museum sites on the Internet. By 2010, these numbers had grown to 785. According to statistical reports of 2011, 1-2% of Internet sites were made up of museum sites. Now it is more than that.

In 1999, at the congress on "Museum and new technologies" held in Russia, the article "Museum Representation on the Internet" by A.V. Lebedeva was published.⁸ That is, he gave the symbolic name of museum sites as museum embassies on the Internet. This article reveals the opportunities that museum sites on the Internet provide in museum activities:

- The museum can participate in the system of local and international organizations;
- A personal site will be an additional opportunity to present its collections in front of the museum;
- mutual qualification information is exchanged between museums through Internet technologies;
- Allows to identify missing resources in the museum system;
- An increase in the number of visitors to the museum will be achieved among Internet users;
- It can be used as an experimental area in the implementation of projects related to the museum.

Today's young visitors to museum websites are the real visitors of tomorrow. For this reason, based on the European experience, museums are creating special museum sites for children. The museum is a rich treasure of cultural information. Museum sites are a tool that allows mutual online cultural cooperation. In order to determine in which category and to what extent the museum is interesting and

⁸ Легеченко М.В. Некоторые аспекты культуры создания музейного веб-сайта// Омский научный вестник. – Омск. 2011 - № 1 (95) С- 209

important, you can find out by conducting online forums, conferences, comments left on the site and the number of visitors.

Today, organizations in almost every field have their own websites on the Internet. Statistical information is undoubtedly of interest to many. Accordingly, a number of observations and polls are canceled on the websites themselves, and nominations on various topics, or "hit-parades" in modern language, are held. Among these, a number of lists have been compiled within museums. A list of "hit museums" such as "The most interesting museum sites", "The most unusual museum sites" has been compiled. Some museums or galleries exist only on the Internet, or their main activity is related to the Internet, while others have both physical and virtual activities. Only the best museums in the online museum category have been selected:

- DiMoDa is an online and tour museum that works in cooperation with art galleries and museums around the world. It allows you to download the exhibitions that have been held online. www.dimoda.art;

- The International Women's Museum is an online museum that does not have a building, and only exhibits online exhibitions that show the global problems of women. Among the exhibitions: "We Imagine Ourselves", "Women, Power and Politics", "Economy: Women and the Global Economy" were held. <https://iawm.international>;

- INMG - Khaqlaro New Media Gallery (International New Media Gallery) is an exhibition site dedicated to the history of art that allows viewing both online and offline, and has also presented its academic catalog. The International New Media Gallery (INMG) is an online museum specializing in the development of image and screen-based art. Founded in 2012, INMG aims to expand the audience for contemporary culture by exhibiting works of art outside the physical walls of the traditional museum, providing an educational base for online and offline discussion. INMG is dedicated to exploring current debates and themes in art history: migration, war, environmental activism, and the internet itself. Today, three exhibitions are organized in the gallery:

- Corrine Silve: moving abroad

- Thomson and Craighead: A Short Film About War

- Amy Balkin: (In)visible Matte.

These lists change over the years according to the activities of the museums. The ranking of museums and museum sites is determined by the number of comments and observations left by visitors to the site.

Following the new modern trends in the development of museums, among foreign museums, the museums of Uzbekistan also have their own websites. Of these:

1. State Museum of History of Uzbekistan - www.history-museum.uz It is somewhat simple in terms of design. But there is enough information and sections to get an idea of the museum. Many events, talks, book presentations related to the museum field, conferences, international competitions are held in the museum and are posted on the site in Uzbek, English and Russian languages. For this top-class museum, the website is its calling card.

2. State Museum of the History of Applied Arts and Crafts of Uzbekistan - www.muzeart.uz. The site of the museum is designed in accordance with its name. But little information is given about the museum collection. There is a brief description of pottery and small plastic and several illustrations. But the museum has other departments and areas of applied art, including carving, wood carving, carpet making, and jewelry. It would be nice to have a little information from them and some examples of their works. The museum's address, page on social networks, museum menu, contact phone number and email address are shown. Another advantage of the website is the contact section, which allows you to book a tour in advance. Another advantage is the placement of scientific articles on applied arts. It is also possible to organize a small virtual tour of the museum. It can be seen on the front page. The most important sign is the certificate sign, which indicates that the site is officially registered.

3. State Art Museum of Uzbekistan - www.stateartmuseum.uz. The achievement section of this site, the information about the museum collection is very nicely presented. Each of the four sections is detailed and illustrated in a quality format. The name of the company that created the museum website is given, and its pages on social networks are also marked.

4. I.V. State Art Museum of the Republic of Karakalpakstan named after Savitsky - www.museum.kr.uz It is designed in a unique way, corresponding to the name of the museum. Information about the museum's collection is given in the appendices.

5. Tashkent Polytechnic Museum - www.politomuseum.uz A website is very important for a modern museum today. Because it is in such a museum that various and interesting exhibitions and open days are held. Rich in collections, the exhibits are very rare and unique. Available in three languages. The

design is carefully crafted to match the name of the museum. There are the most necessary and basic sections. Addresses that allow you to contact the museum are indicated.

6. Museum of the history of communication - www.aloqamuzey.uz It is simple in design, organized without excessive decorations, but the fact that it is possible to find the most necessary and basic information and to order an excursion in advance can be said to be one of the achievements of this site.

7. Repression Victims Memorial Museum - www.muzei-khotira.uz is one of the most prestigious museums in Uzbekistan. In terms of design, it has very interesting sections, although it is a simple-looking design without excessive decorations. Multimedia is well used. There is a video clip, written letters from honored guests, address, museum contact point, search section, and the most unique part is the possibility to monitor the font of the site in any size.

8. Khiva open-air museum - <http://www.khivamuseum.uz> this site can give a very good impression of the city of Khiva. The web page template is also very well chosen. Brief digital information about the ancient city, information about the historical monuments of the city of Khiva. What makes the site even more interesting is the Khiva 360 section, where you can take a virtual tour of the open-air museum.

Several other museums have similar websites. Although some museums do not have their own websites, you can see their activity on social networks. Among them, A. Qakhor House-Museum, Olympic Fame Museum, Urol Tansikbayev House-Museum, Oybek House-Museum have pages on Facebook social networks. Among them, the most active museum is the Museum of Olympic Fame. Medals and trophies won by our athletes are displayed almost every day.

www.tripadvisor.com, terabayt.uz, and rd.uz sites have information about existing museums, galleries, shrines in Uzbekistan and their addresses, as well as brief information about them. In this way, the interest of visiting the museum itself is aroused by viewing the personal websites of the remaining museums. But there is not enough information on this. There are a number of companies developing software or creating virtual museum sites. Of these, the site www.panoramio.uz has the ability to create digital virtual museums in 3D format.

In conclusion, there are many interesting, historical and modern museums in Uzbekistan, and they must be introduced to the world. Among them, the State Museum of the History of Uzbekistan, the Museum of Applied Arts of Uzbekistan, the State Art Museum of Uzbekistan, the Museum of Communication History, the Museum of Oriental Miniature Art named after Kamoliddin Behzod, A.

Qahhor, Yunus Rajabi, Mukhtar Ashrafiy, Urol Tansikbayev house museums and other museums are known and famous among the people and foreign tourists. But few museums have their own website. This, of course, first of all comes down to money. But today, among the modern methods of advertising, it is necessary to open pages on the Internet, more precisely, on social networks, Facebook, Instagram, thereby increasing the number of visitors, and more widely covering the activities of the museum. Visiting virtual museums through the Internet site is used as an interactive textbook for art lovers not only in higher education institutions, but also in schools, and young people will have a sense of respect for their people, the history and future of the Motherland, the preservation of traditions, culture, and a religious background. It increases feelings of citizenship and responsibility for the future of one's country.

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